

Digital Innovation: Intelligent Traffic Control System (ITCS)

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The proposed digital innovation project seeks to develop an intelligent traffic control system that will help improve traffic management, surveillance by automatically enforcing traffic regulations thereby facilitating a smooth vehicular flow and reduce traffic incidents. The system will consist of a camera(s) and a vehicle monitoring device equipped with number plate sensing technology (ANPR). The camera will be able to detect vehicles speeding beyond the legal limit, vehicles violating red lights or stop lanes and vehicles using lanes not designated for them. The ANPR technology will enable the system to be able to automatically ticket offenders based on their recognized number plates (Bramberger, et al., 2006, p.68).

Traffic congestion is currently one of the most critical problems facing many parts of the world particularly large urban cities. According to a number of recent studies, traffic congestion is currently costing the global economy billions of dollars in terms of the time lost in traffic, lost productivity and fuel wastage (Yousef et al., 2010, p.753). Although no exact conditions under which traffic jams occur has never been fully predicted, many experts believe traffic jams and congestion occur when the available road capacity cannot accommodate the volume of traffic generated at a particular time. This is mostly cause or aggravate traffic incidents like accidents or even when a single vehicle violates the traffic regulations.

Congestion occurring on roads ultimately breed slow-paced traffic, consequently increasing the period of travel, leading to loss of money and fuel, hence rendered notable as part of the great concerns in the transport arena. There is no doubt that emergency vehicle such as fire trucks and ambulances would need to get by their intended destinations at the earliest time possible. There is therefore an utmost necessity to establish an economical, fast and effective traffic control system to aid national development. Given the ever-rising count of vehicles on roads, it is worthwhile for traffic monitoring authorities to determine new ways to overcome.

Video: Analysis of economic-loss from the traffic jam in India

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0g9bbSw720A>

Audio

Clip: <http://www.radionz.co.nz/national/programmes/morningreport/audio/201757790/oe-cd-report-highlights-issues-with-nz-housing>

According to the audio clip recently produced by Roads and Maritime Services of New Zealand, the traditional manual or semi-automated traffic controls that are currently in use in many cities and countries around the world are not effective and are largely dependent on man power to control traffic. Chen and Cheng (2010) suggest that traffic police officers are normally allotted at different locations on the highways and cities to

help control traffic. In most countries, the traffic police officers are often required to carry sign boards and a whistle. They are also required to put on special uniforms to make them be easily visible to drivers.

Another traffic control system commonly used is the traditional Vehicle Actuated Control System whereby traffic light equipped with timers automatically change color from Red to Green. A major disadvantage of the Vehicle Actuated Control Systems as a traffic control system is that it uses algorithms that they will still show red even when the traffic has passed until the counter is completed. As a result, they do little to ease traffic congestion since the counter does not consider the traffic density.

Traditional Traffic Control Light Signal

Recent researches have focused on developing automated traffic light systems equipped with both timers and electrical sensors which are able to detect vehicular density and reduce the time being wasted by a green light when the road is empty (Wang, 2003, p.1313). Nevertheless, many of the contemporary traffic control and management systems are still inadequate for managing high vehicular density and do not have the capacity to meet the increasing number of vehicles in many cities, urban areas and roads

(Naphade et al, 2011, p.33)... Generally, the current digital innovation technology will particularly provide a number of important benefits for traffic control and management some of which include:

1. Traffic flow monitoring by enabling the identification of traffic accidents .
2. Enforcement of various traffic management measures such as speed limits, red-light infringements and traffic regulation orders.
3. Use of (ANPR) Technology to enhance speed monitoring and management of Vehicular flow.

Fig 1: 3D Representation of the Proposed Intelligent Traffic Control System

Figure 2: The proposed intelligent traffic control system will be able to detect vehicles violating red lights and other traffic rules

How Automatic Number plate Recognition Works

ANPR particularly uses optical character recognition to detect and reads number plates on vehicles (Kranthi and Pranathi, 2011). The system comprised of specialized CCTV cameras with inbuilt optical character recognition software that enable them to number plates on both still and moving vehicles as shown in the diagram below.

Fig 3: *How ANPR Technology works*

Video on How ANPR Technology works

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=utWYPTk-86U>

Figure 4: *Automatic Number plate Recognition Process (NEC, 2015)*

Video: Demonstration of the Automatic Number plate Recognition Process

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tp-3lo3Blp0>

Demonstration: *control for the individual lane*

Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O_iGQI5pUPQ

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